

The Structure of Electrons and the Origin of Electromagnetic Forces

Wentao Wang

(Dated. June 28, 2025)

Abstract

There maybe ether in the universe, and the structure of electrons resembles that of cyclones on Earth, with an inward attractive force that constitutes gravitational force. The results of the Michelson-Morley experiment can be attributed to the Earth being composed of many similar electron-like vortices, which drag the surrounding ether as it moves forward. When the distance from the Earth is not far enough, gravitational force still plays a role, it still drags the surrounding ether, resulting in equal light speeds measured in two different directions. This paper explores the mechanism of electromagnetic force formation, causes and calculations of gravitational force formation, relativistic causes, and other issues.

Keywords: Ether, electric field force, Lorentz force, weak interaction, black holes.

1. The Structure of Electrons

In the observable universe, there is a uniform distribution of smaller particles, similar to Earth's atmosphere. The electrons are these vortices in the Etheric gas, similar to cyclones on Earth, as shown in Figure 1. The side view is illustrated in Figure 2.

On the upper side of the electron cyclone, as the distance is lengthened, the upward erupting airflow is pulled down due to the attraction of the low pressure at the center of the electron cyclone, so there is no erupting airflow above the electron cyclone. On the lower side of the electron cyclone, the inward-absorbing spiral airflow will not disappear as the distance is lengthened, but will always be there, so that, from a distance, the cyclone will only have inward-absorbing spiral airflow from below, as

shown in Figure 3.

Figure 1

Figure 2

electron

positron

Figure 3

The inward suction from the electron or particle vortex produces gravity, and the inward spiral attraction from the lower part of the vortex produces electromagnetism. The mass of the electron is specified as the total mass of Ether missing from the low pressure at the center of the electron vortex. Since the vortices in the Ether may not be the same size, the mass of each electron may not be the same size. But in Figure 2, the lower end low pressure of the vortex is a critical value because the low pressure in the center is not enough to attract the surrounding airflow to rotate, so it can only attract the airflow from the bottom up to fill it, or that the rotation caused by their bottoms is equal, so they cause equal rotational effort to the upwardly inhaled airflow at their bottoms, since charge is determined by rotational effort (explained in section 5), so different vortexes have the same amount of charge to show to the outside world. At a

distance, around the swirling surface of the vortex, the direction is almost vertically inward because the attraction of the center is not strong enough to cause rotational motion of the Ether.

2.Explanation of Michaelson-Moray Experimental

Results

From the structure of an electron or particle, due to the attraction of the vortex to the surrounding, it can be understood that small particles are dragged by the moving Earth. When the distance from the Earth is not too far, these small particles follow the Earth's movement. In the Michelson-Morley experiment, the measured light speeds were equal because the distance from the Earth was not too great.

3. Origin of gravity

The inward attractive force of the electron cyclone generates gravitational force. The gravitational mass of the electron is equal to the mass of the portion of Ether that is less in the middle low-pressure portion than around it. The inertial mass of the electron is equal to the mass of the portion of Ether that the electron center attracts to rotate with it to fill it, and since they are balanced overall, they are equal. Other spinning particles may have a structure similar to that of electrons. The gravitational force produced collectively by multiple particles is proportional to their mass product and inversely proportional to the square of the distance between them. When the distance is R , the inward attraction of a large number of electron vortices can be regarded as uniformly distributed on a spherical surface of radius R . And the total magnitude of the attractive force is invariant with distance. Take a unit mass of a substance and set its total attraction to the outside world to be F_0 . Setting the attractive pressure of the vortex attracted around here to P , it can be shown that

$$P = \frac{F_0}{4\pi R^2}$$

Taking another substance of unit mass, the total area of the cross-section of this substance subjected to attractive pressure is set as S_0 , the gravitational force between two unit masses is set to F' ,

Find,

$$F' = P \cdot S_0 = \frac{F_0}{4\pi R^2} \cdot S_0 = \frac{S_0 F_0}{4\pi R^2}$$

This is the case when only the vortices of one unit mass object attract the vortices of another unit mass object. When an object of mass m_1 attracts another object of mass m_2 , since every vortex of that object attracts all the vortices of that other object, and every unit mass of that object attracts all the unit masses of that other object, let the unit mass be m_0 , The number of units of mass contained in m_1 is n_1 , The number of units of mass contained in m_2 is n_2 , so, $n_1 = \frac{m_1}{m_0}$, $n_2 = \frac{m_2}{m_0}$,

So,

$$F = F' \cdot (n_1 \times n_2) = \frac{S_0 F_0}{4\pi R^2} (n_1 \times n_2) = \frac{S_0 F_0}{4\pi R^2} \left(\frac{m_1}{m_0} \times \frac{m_2}{m_0} \right) = \frac{S_0 F_0}{4\pi m_0^2} \cdot \frac{m_1 m_2}{R^2}$$

Order $\frac{S_0 F_0}{4\pi m_0^2} = G$,

We get,

$$F = \frac{S_0 F_0}{4\pi m_0^2} \cdot \frac{m_1 m_2}{R^2} = G \frac{m_1 m_2}{R^2}$$

As with the traditional formula for the expression of gravity.

4. Origin of the time dilation effect and mass-energy equation

4.1. The existence of small particles easily explains why the speed of light is invariant. Light is a mechanical wave pushed outward during electron vibrations, so its speed remains constant. Because the overall speed of the light wave does not change, when a system moves forward, the change in the velocity component of the light wave in the perpendicular direction can be determined using the right triangle model (as shown in Figure 4).

Figure 4

Find,

$$v' = \sqrt{c^2 - v^2}$$

Therefore, for the same event and the same distance, for example, L , all values are equal,

Find,

$$t = \frac{L}{c}, \quad t' = \frac{L}{\sqrt{c^2 - v^2}}$$

So,

$$t' = \frac{c}{\sqrt{c^2 - v^2}} t$$

Same as Einstein's time dilation formula. It can produce length contraction and time dilation effects.

4.2. The mechanical waves formed inside the electron due to centripetal attraction can also be regarded as a kind of light wave. The energy of a light wave can be calculated using the methods for mechanical waves, specifically kinetic energy plus potential energy, and the result is mass multiplied by the square of the speed of light. This is the same as the mass-energy equivalence formula. For example, in the electron, the mechanical wave velocity of light composed of rotating small particles is the speed of light (c). In university-level physics, by using the infinitesimal element

method to calculate the kinetic and potential energies of mechanical waves, one can find that they are equal, and,

$$dE_k = dE_p = \frac{1}{2} A^2 w^2 \sin^2 \left[w \left(t - \frac{x}{u} \right) + \phi_0 \right] dm$$

So,

$$E_k = E_p$$

Also, Furthermore, analyzing each photon mechanical wave attracted toward the center within the electron vortex, it can be considered as a mechanical wave with pressure relative to its surroundings moving inward, similar to a sound wave in air. The electron mass is defined as the mass equivalent to the ether pressure difference between the low-pressure region at the center of the electron vortex and the surrounding area.

Taking a sound wave as an example, suppose this sound wave pressure hits a wall. The potential energy and kinetic energy contained within are entirely converted into thermal energy. Through a force analysis of the work done by the potential energy, this process can also be seen as the wall doing work on the pressure (as illustrated in Figure 5). Here, m is the excess air mass in the pressure region compared to the surroundings. Since the sound wave moves only half of its own length for each small microelement in the process, it can be viewed as the sound wave moving only half of its own wavelength L_0 , set the work distance to L , so,

$$L = \frac{L_0}{2}$$

Since the extra pressure somewhere in the sound wave is proportional to the density of the portion of itself that is more than the surrounding area, i.e., to the mass of the portion of air that is more than the surrounding area, i.e., to m , the pressure generated by each portion is exactly proportional to its own mass. When viewed as work done by the wall on the sound wave, each part of the sound wave is subjected to an equal acceleration, set the acceleration to be a , set the process time to be t , since the process is uniformly decelerating, so,

$$a = \frac{\Delta v}{\Delta t} = \frac{c - 0}{t} = \frac{c}{t},$$

And it can be seen that the sound wave length

$$L_0 = c \cdot t = ct$$

So,

$$W = FL = ma \cdot L = m \cdot \frac{c}{t} \cdot \frac{L_0}{2} = m \cdot \frac{c}{t} \cdot \frac{ct}{2} = \frac{1}{2}mc^2$$

i.e.,

$$E_p = W = \frac{1}{2}mc^2$$

Figure 5

And because

$$E_k = E_p$$

So,

$$E = E_k + E_p = 2E_p = 2 \times \frac{1}{2}mc^2 = mc^2$$

i.e.,

$$E = mc^2$$

It is the same as the traditional mass-energy equation.

when the vortex structure is destroyed, all this energy is released, i.e., nuclear energy, with mass being entirely converted into energy.

5. Origin of electric field force

In Section 1 we know that at a distance there is no airflow in the upper part of the electron vortex, leaving only a spiral attracting airflow below, as in Figure 3. This lower airflow can be transmitted far away. The magnetic field consists of rotating photons. The rotation direction corresponds to the magnetic field direction, and the perpendicular direction of rotation of the magnetic field as the direction of electric field. When two electrons, one positively charged and the other negatively charged, meet (as shown in Figure 6), they attract each other due to the consistency of the airflow direction, as the internal pressure of the moving fluid diminishes. This principle comes from the principle of Bernoulli. This generates an electric field force. When two same-charged particles encounter each other, they collide more frequently due to the opposing directions of the two fluid streams, resulting in repulsive force. This principle also originates from Bernoulli's principle. This is similar to the force acting on a rotating ping pong ball in the air.

Figure 6

6. Magnetic field force

The origin of magnetic field force is also similar to a rotating ping pong ball (as shown in Figure 7). As when the electron is moving forward, its vortex rotation surface will be perpendicular to the forward direction, so when the electron is in the magnetic field along the perpendicular to the direction of the magnetic field, the structure is shown in Figure 7, the direction of movement of the electron is perpendicular to the surface of the paper. According to Bernoulli's principle, the pressure on the top of the pressure decreases, and the pressure on the bottom of the pressure increases, so the overall is subjected to an upward force, which is perpendicular to the magnetic field, perpendicular to the direction of movement, in

line with the left-handed rule.

Figure 7

7. Electromagnetic relationship

From the structure of the electron, the relationship between the divergence and curl of the charge and the magnetic field can be seen, i.e., the Maxwell equations:

1. There is a rotating magnetic field around the electron, and the divergence of the magnetic field is zero.
2. The divergence of the charge depends on the magnitude of the charge.
3. When there is no current, the directions of the electrons in the conductor are random, and the sum of the magnetic fields around the electrons is also random, thus showing no external magnetic field. When a conductor is pierced by an electric field, the electrons inside the conductor will be moved by the electric field, resulting in the movement of electrons in the same direction, the vortex of electrons rotating in the same direction, the vortex is the magnetic field, so it leads to the same direction of the magnetic field, so the external display of the rotating magnetic field, and is perpendicular to the direction of the current. The movement of the electrons will neutralize the charges at the poles of the electric field and will reduce the external electric field, resulting in a change in the electric field, and this change in the electric field is caused by the movement of the electrons. So to the outside world, it appears that the electric field change is synchronized with the magnetic field generation. It is actually caused by electrons being in the same direction.
4. When a closed conductor cuts through a uniform magnetic field, it is equivalent to each electron within the conductor moving perpendicular to the field, and each electron is subjected to the Lorentz force (e.g., Section 6, e.g., Figure 7). According to

Bernoulli's principle, this causes each electron to move in the same direction (like rotating ping-pong balls in motion), generating an electric field and current. Since the faster the electrons move, which is equivalent to a ping-pong ball moving forward faster, the greater the force, it manifests itself externally as the faster the magnetic flux changes, the greater the force on the conductor.

8. Weak force

The weak force should be the disturbance caused by small particles nearby the atoms, while the strong force comes into play when matter gets sufficiently close, causing gravitational forces to no longer disperse but instead effectively attract each other, similar to two cyclones approaching each other.

9. Black hole

A black hole may be formed by a huge planet without enough support; due to overwhelmingly strong gravitational forces, small "vortices" get crushed, resulting in a new large "vortex." This "vortex" is the black hole. Thus, a black hole is of small volume, rotating, and structurally similar to an electron.

10. Double-slit experiment

From the structure of electrons, it can be inferred that electrons represent a type of wave, but are perceived macroscopically as particles, hence in the double-slit interference experiment, they simultaneously pass through both slits and exhibit interference.

11. Quantum entanglement

When two electrons get close, they interact due to the attractive force between their "vortices", merging into a single entity, expressing externally the nature of a whole, akin to a double vortex, which should represent quantum entanglement.

Conclusion: Matter is not particles but waves. There exists absolute time that does not change; space also remains unchanged, and only the observer and small particles undergo change.